

Molecular Modelling Methods

Three structures of LXR α (5HJS, 3IPS and 3LOE) and two structures of LXR β (1PQ6 and 1PQ9) were selected based on the chemical similarity of their co-crystallized ligands with sorafenib and were retrieved from the PDB server. Selected proteins were prepared by adding hydrogens, adjusting protonation states of amino-acids and fixing missing side-chain atoms and protein loops (PrepWiz, Maestro v2018.2). All co-crystallized ligands and sorafenib were re-drawn with the 2D-sketcher (Maestro v2018.2), with stereochemistry determined from the literature, and minimized with force-field OPLS3e followed by correction of their protonation state using LigPrep.

Molecular docking was performed within a determined 10 Å grid around the co-crystallized in the ligand binding pocket (LBP) or, in case of the AF-2 region, by residues interacting with the co-crystallized peptide of the nuclear receptor coactivator 1 (NCOA1). For the AF-2 region, only X-ray crystal structures with co-crystallized co-activator peptide were considered (3IPS and 3LOE). For each compound 80 docking runs were carried out, using the default settings of the Glide program (Glide v7.7, Maestro v2018.2) in extra-precision mode⁵⁶. Amino-acid residues were considered rigid during the calculation, but hydroxyl groups were allowed to rotate. Redocking of co-crystallized ligands in the LBP resulted in top-ranked docking poses with heavy atom root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) below 1 Å in comparison with the original conformation, for all employed PDB structures. Docking poses were clustered by RMSD and a representative pose from the most populated cluster and the top-ranked pose by docking score were visually inspected. Chosen docking poses for each sorafenib within LXR α (PDB ID: 3IPS) and LXR β 's ligand binding pocket (1PQ6) and LXR α 's AF-2 groove underwent molecular dynamics (MD) simulation to evaluate ligand stability within the site and analyse its interactions.

MD simulations were carried out using Desmond engine [1] with the OPLS3e force-field [2]. Also, along this force-field represent the halogen bonds by an off-atom charge sites, which is a suitable for the ligands of this series. The simulated system encompassed the protein-ligand complex, a predefined water model (simple point charge, TIP3P [3]) as a solvent and

counterions (four ions of Na⁺ were added to neutralize the overall system charge). The system was treated in a cubic box with periodic boundary conditions specifying the shape and the size of the box as 13 Å distance from the box edges to any atom of the protein. We used a time step of 1 fs, the short-range coulombic interactions were treated using a cut-off value of 9.0 Å using the short-range method, while the smooth Particle Mesh Ewald method (PME) handled long-range coulombic interactions [4].

Initially, the relaxation of the system was performed using Steepest Descent and the limited-memory Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno algorithms in a hybrid manner. The simulation was performed under NPT ensemble for 5 ns implementing the Berendsen thermostat and barostat methods. A constant temperature of 310 K was maintained throughout the simulation using the Nose-Hoover thermostat algorithm and Martyna-Tobias-Klein Barostat algorithm to maintain 1 atm of pressure, respectively. After minimization and relaxation of the system, we proceeded with the production step of 200 ns. All MD simulations were performed at least in three independent runs with randomly generated seeds. The representative structure was selected by visual inspection of the protein-ligand interactions and figures were generated using PyMol (v2.4.3, Schrödinger, Inc., New York, USA).

Common LXR agonists show different interaction profile with residues in the LBP, which although distal to AF-2, can still promote cation- π interaction between a conserved histidine (421, LXR α numbering) on helix 10/11 and tryptophan (443) on the C-terminal activation function-2 (AF-2) helix. This electrostatic interaction stabilizes the C-terminal helix 12, to form a binding groove for specific coactivator proteins, such as NCOA1 [5].

Sorafenib docking poses in the LBP reveal two important hydrogen bonds, one with the hydroxyl from Thr302, and another between the amide carbonyl group from sorafenib and the main-chain oxygen atom of Leu316. Similarly, an X-ray structure of [4-(3-([2-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl)benzyl])(2,2-diphenylethyl)amino)propoxy)-1H-indol-1-yl]acetic acid bound to LXR α (PDB ID: 3FC6) shows that one of the carboxylate oxygens of can form a hydrogen bond

with the backbone NH of Leu314, while the other forms a salt bridge interaction with Arg303 and Asn223 [6].

The chloro-trifluoromethylbenzyl group from the original ligand, F₃-methylAA (PDB ID: 3IPS), is surrounded by a hydrophobic cavity composed of Ile295, Leu299, Met298, Phe254 and Phe257. These interactions are identical with those observed in the LXR β /GW3965 complex (PDB ID: 1PQ6) and the LXR α /F₃-methylAA (PDB ID: 3IPS) [7]. Interestingly, sorafenib's 1-chloro-2-(trifluoromethyl)benzene is also stable within a hydrophobic pocket composed of Phe257, Phe326, Phe340, Leu299, Ile339 and Trp443 (LXR α numbering). Tryptophan (443) belongs to the helix-12, which composes the AF2 groove, therefore we could hypothesize that sorafenib hydrophobic interaction is responsible by maintaining the conformation of this region, directly collaborating to the interaction with the NCOA1 peptide. From the ligand binding pocket perspective, modelling results suggest that sorafenib would interact with LXR α in a similar manner as LXR β , accessing similar hydrophobic pockets and accessing a similar hydrogen bond network by interacting with Leu330 (LXR β numbering), but with His435 instead of the respective threonine.

On the AF2 region, sorafenib docking pose initially suggested interactions with Gln300, Glu455 and Lys287. These last two amino-acids compose the salt bridge, which position the NCOA1 peptide (PDB ID: 3L0E and 3IPS). However, simulations of sorafenib on the AF-2 region did not maintain stable interactions with key-amino-acids, such as the charge clamp (Glu441 and Lys273), which does not support a stable binding to this region.

References